

Research

Factors Contributing to Poor Performance in Mathematics in Bauchi State

Sagir A. Mahmud^{1*}, Hamisu Idi², Muhammad Mubarak Muhammad³, Abubakar Adamu⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, Nigeria

*Corresponding author:

Accepted: 12 December, 2020; Online: 23 December, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4391345>

Abstract: *The study examined, ascertained and described the factors that influence poor performance on mathematics with reference to school based factors, parent's socio-economic factors and students' factors in senior secondary schools in Bauchi. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The target population was 4789 students, 132 mathematics teachers and 12 head teachers as respondents out of which 369 students, 132 head teachers as well as all the 12 head teachers were randomly selected and studied. The data was collected by the use of three structured questionnaires; student, teachers and head teachers' questionnaires. Results of the study revealed that school based factors, parent's socio-economic factors and students' related factors have a significant effect on students' Mathematics performance. It is also revealed that there are negative factors affecting teachers' effectiveness in teaching Mathematics. It is recommended that the finding will give the stakeholders an insight into emerging issues on performance and influence the Ministry of Education (MOE), State Universal Basic Education Board (SEBEB), Teaching Services Commission (TSC) and other decision makers on policy formulation such as supervision and inspection by proper authorities, organizing mathematics inter and intra school competition, as well as enlightenment of parents on importance of children's education. An awareness of these factors can help increase a teacher's effectiveness if they are dealt.*

Keywords: *Poor Performance, Mathematics, Public Senior Secondary Schools, Factors*

Introduction

Mathematics is the language without which science, commerce, industry, the internet, and the entire global economic infrastructure are struck dumb. Mathematics is regarded as a pillar of almost all the streams in academics given its importance in tertiary education and most careers. It is not only beneficial but also essential. Hence, Mathematics is not only a language and a subject in it, but it is also critical in fostering logical and rigorous thinking; as such its influence is

immense. The failure rate of mathematics in secondary schools is alarming as indicated in the table below.

Years	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Mean Scores	14.45	12.72	15.89	13.44	18.25	16.61	13.23	12.23	18.72	17.62

Table 1: WAEC Performance in Mathematics

Performance in mathematics as reflected by the WAEC results has remained poor over the years. Hence, the need to investigate factors contributing to poor performance by students in mathematics at WAEC examinations by students in Bauchi state so that poor performance in mathematics can be reversed. The student factors, socio cultural factors and school based factors were investigated as independent variables, and achievement in mathematics as the dependent variable. Figure 1 showing the dependent and independent variable.

Figure 1: Dependent and Independent Variable.

Objective of the research

The objectives of the study are:

1. To Determine the school based factors that affect students performance in mathematics
2. To Determine parent's socio-economic factors that affect students performance in mathematics
3. To Determine student related factors that affect student performance in mathematics

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were established:

1. H_{01} : School-based factors do not affect mathematics performance.
2. H_{02} : Parent's socio-economic factors do not affect mathematics performance.
3. H_{03} : Student's factors do not affect mathematics performance.

Literature Review

Mathematics is enshrined in the National Policy on Education (NPE) as a core and compulsory subject for all primary and post-primary school students in Nigeria (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2004). This is largely because of the indispensable role it plays in the advancement of science and technology of any nation (Barnard, 2009). The success of development and provision of quality and excellent results in national examinations depends on the quality of school administration. The better the quality, the better the performance of students will be (Tata et al., 2014).

Many studies presented many causes of poor performance in mathematics among students. For instance, Duke, (2000) in Tshabalala and Ncube, (2013) was of the view that shortage of well trained teachers, inadequate of teaching facilities, lack of fund to purchase necessary equipment, poor quality of textbooks, large classes, poorly motivated teachers, lack of laboratories and libraries, poorly coordinated supervisory activities, interference of the school system by the civil service, incessant transfers of teachers and principals, automatic promotions of pupils, the negative role of public examinations on the teaching learning process and inequality in education opportunities all hamper the smooth acquisition of mathematics knowledge. In addition to the above, causes of poor performance in mathematics, STAN, (2002) as cited by Ojimba, (2012) was of the view that prominent causes of poor performance in mathematics are: Acute shortage of qualified professional mathematics teachers, exhibition of poor knowledge of mathematics content by many mathematics teachers, overcrowded mathematics classrooms, students negative attitude toward mathematics, undue emphasis on the coverage of mathematics syllabus at the expense of meaningful learning of mathematics concepts and inadequate facilities and mathematics laboratories (Adams, 1996; US Department of Education, 2003; Eamon, 2005; NIED, 2010; Tshabalala and Ncube, 2013 and APA, 2016).

Other causes include misconceptions of the subject (mathematics) as difficult one, fear and anxiety by the students (Hanes, 2008). Wikipedia Free Encyclopedia, (2014) stated that students often develop mathematical anxiety in schools, often as a result of learning from teachers who are themselves anxious about their mathematical abilities in certain areas. Attwood, (2014) attributed poor performance in mathematics to parental attitude, interrupted teaching, poor teaching and dyscalculia. Karue and Amukowa, (2013) pointed out that lack of meaningful library and laboratory, qualified teachers, home environmental factors and family backgrounds as well as little participation of parents in the education of their children as the main causes of poor performance in mathematics.

Keeping in view all these discussions, this study was conducted to examine the effect of different factors on the students' quality of academic achievement at the secondary school level in a metropolitan city of Bauchi state with special reference to school related factors, parent's socio-economic factors and students' related factors. Moreover, increasing evidence supports the link between socio - economic status and educational outcomes.

- Low socio - economic status and exposure to adversity are linked to decreased educational success (Hanes, 2008). Early experiences and environmental influences can have a lasting impact on learning (linguistic, cognitive and socio – emotional skills), behavior, and health (Kirkup, 2008).
- Children from low socio - economic status families often begin kindergarten with significantly less linguistic knowledge (Krashen, 2005). As such, children from low-Children from less-advantaged homes score at least 10% lower than the national average on national achievement scores in mathematics and reading (McCoy, 2005).
- Children from less-advantaged homes score at least 10% lower than the national average on national achievement scores in mathematics and reading (McCoy, 2005)
- Children in impoverished settings are much more likely to be absent from school throughout their educational experiences (Roberts, 2007), further increasing the learning gap between them and their wealthier peers.
- While national high school dropout rates have steadily declined, dropout rates for children living in poverty have steadily increased. Low-income students fail to graduate

at 5 times the rate of middle-income families and 6 times that of higher income youth (National Center for Education Statistics, 2016)

Materials and methods

The population of this study was of 4789 SSS III Students in 187 Secondary Schools, 132 mathematics teachers and 24 head teachers (Annual School Census, 2015) out of which 369 students were selected using Taro Yamane’s formula. The sample includes all the teachers and head teachers. The student’s questionnaire comprised sections on demographic data with items such as gender, age, secondary school entry marks, socio-economic and cultural factors, school based factors with items such as method of teaching by teachers, availability of teaching and learning materials, academic qualification, and teaching experience of mathematics teachers and motivation. Mathematics teachers and head teachers questionnaires had sections on demographic data items such as gender, age, academic qualification, and teaching experience. And school based factors with items such as method of teaching, availability of teaching and learning materials, workload and motivation. Correlation and regression techniques were used and analyzed the data.

Result and Discussion

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.886	.784	.783	3.99334

Source: Computed from the data collected using SPSS

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	21340.088	3	7113.363	446.068	.000
	Residual	5868.423	368	15.947		
	Total	27208.511	371			

Source: Computed from the data collected using SPSS

The coefficient of multiple correlation showed a strong and positive relationship of the mathematics performance and other variables, with ($R = 0.886$). R – square, the coefficient of determination is 0.784. This showed that 78.4% of the total variation is explained by the changes in the independent variables indicating that school-based factors, parent’s socio-economic factors and students’ factors explained mathematics performance by 78.4%. Result showed that if these variables (school-based factors, parent’s socio-economic factors and students’ factors) were adequately intervened and funded, mathematics performance will get enhanced significantly. This is justified by the value in ANOVA as the P – value is less than the level of significance (P value = $0.000 < 0.05$) indicating a positive impact. **Coefficients**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-9.393	.879		-10.684	.000
	School-based Factors	7.981	.905	1.019	8.823	.000
	Parent’s Socio-economic Factors	3.451	.724	.404	4.766	.000
	Students’ Factors	4.325	1.145	.531	3.778	.000

Source: Computed from the data collected using SPSS

Multiple regression analysis was carried out to determine the combine effect of these factors. All the predictors yielded significant beta weights with their varied t – values which are all statistically significant in each case.

1. The predictor, school-based factors had a beta weight of $\beta_1 = 7.981$ with its P - value that is statistically significant ($P = 0.000 < 0.05$) indicating its impact, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis and concluding that school-based factors has a significant effects on mathematics performance.
2. Result showed that parent’s socio-economic factor has beta weight of $\beta_2 = 3.451$ with its corresponding P -value of 0.000. This showed that the calculated P -value is less than the level of significant ($P = 0.000 < 0.05$) which is statistically significant and hence, we reject the null hypothesis and concluded that parent’s socio-economic factors has

significantly affect mathematics performance.

3. The predictor, students' factors has a beta weight of $\beta_3 = 4.325$ with its P- value that is statistically significant ($P = 0.000 < 0.05$) indicating its impact, which form the basis of rejecting the null hypothesis and concluding that students' related factors has a significant effect on mathematics performance.

Discussion

School Based Factors

It is disheartening to note that with all the importance attached to mathematics in Nigeria's education system, poor performance is recorded in public examinations in recent time (Tata et al., 2014). This poor performance in mathematics is one of the major reasons for decline in science and technology courses and development itself. Ojimba, (2012) was of the view that without mathematics, there is no science, without science there is no modern technology and without modern technology there is no modern society. Despite the importance attached to mathematics by all stakeholders in education, senior secondary school students still perform poorly. For instance, result has it that school-based factors impacted positively on mathematics performance because it played an important role which includes school structures and organizations, class room arrangement, conduciveness and management are to put into considerations. According to Munda et al., (2000) physical facilities contribute positively to students' academic performance. Rouse and Barrow (2006) who observes that availability of and quality of textbooks in a secondary school is strongly related to achievement among children from lower income families especially those in rural boarding schools, that physical facilities contribute positively to students academic performance (Munda et al., 2000).

Teachers factors also need to be looked as Duke (2000) in Tshabalala and Ncube, (2013) was of the view that shortage of well trained teachers, inadequate of teaching facilities, lack of fund to purchase necessary equipment, poor quality of textbooks, large classes, poorly motivated teachers, lack of laboratories and libraries, poorly coordinated supervisory activities, interference of the school system by the civil service, incessant transfers of teachers and principals, automatic promotions of pupils, the negative role of public examinations on the teaching learning process. According to the scheme of work as enshrined by the Ministry of Education (2008) a teacher in a secondary school is supposed to teach at most 30 lessons in a week. Data obtained and analyzed by Tata et al. (2014) showed that 27.8% of Mathematics teachers teach below 15 lessons per

week, 66.7% teach between 16 to 30 lessons, while 27.8% teach more than 30 lessons in a week. This indicates that 27.8% of mathematics teachers are overloaded. This percentage is high and may contribute to poor performance in mathematics.

Parent's Socio-economic Factors

Increasing evidence supports the link between parent's socio-economic status and educational outcomes of their children. Low socio-economic status and exposure to adversity are linked to decreased educational success (Hanes, 2008). Early experiences and environmental influences can have a lasting impact on learning (linguistic, cognitive and socio-emotional skills), behavior, and health (Kirkup, 2008). Children from low socio-economic status families often begin kindergarten with significantly less linguistic knowledge (Krashen, 2005). As such, children from less-advantaged homes score at least 10% lower than the national average on national achievement scores in mathematics and reading (McCoy, 2005). Children in impoverished settings are much more likely to be absent from school throughout their educational experiences (Roberts, 2007), further increasing the learning gap between them and their wealthier peers. While national high school dropout rates have steadily declined, dropout rates for children living in poverty have steadily increased. Low-income students fail to graduate at 5 times the rate of middle-income families and 6 times that of higher income youth (National Center for Education Statistics, 2016). Result showed that there is a significant impact of socio-economic factor on mathematics performance. Similarly, Desarrollo (2007) indicated that the extent to which parents or other family members are actively engaged in a student's education had a positive influence on the student's achievement.

Students' Factors

Students' related factors contributing to poor performance were found to be, parent's socio-economic background, peer factor, and laziness towards mathematics. Findings corresponds that of Mbugua et al., (2012), Karue and Amukowa, (2013) and Ojimba, (2012) who found out that creation of positive attitude toward mathematics, provision of proper staffing, teacher-students ratio, cooperative and child-centered approaches in teaching mathematics and maintaining teacher-students relation are some of the ways of improving performance in mathematics in students which in turn reduce mathematics anxiety. Haimowitz (1989) indicated the cause of most failures in schools might not be due to insufficient or inadequate instruction but by active

resistance by the learners. Mwamwenda (1995) argued that the achievement of students in a subject is determined by their attitudes rather than inability to study.

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Acknowledgments

All praises and thanks be to the Almighty Allah for giving us the gift of life and good health. I would like to express my special thanks and deepest appreciation to the management of the Federal Polytechnic Bauchi, the Research office and the Tertiary Education Trust Fund(TETFUND) for their support in making this study a success.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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